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Mastering speech culture is one of the most necessary conditions for the formation of a socially active personality. The tasks of teaching at school are diverse. The primary one is the ability to clearly and express your thoughts clearly in free oral and written form, speak correctly, have a well-modulated voice, be able to express your emotions with the appropriate intonation, observe speech culture and develop the ability to communicate. Accordingly, we consider the development of speech culture to be one of the main tasks at the present stage of student education.

Keywords: speech culture, intellectual activity, language, psychology, linguistics, communicative tasks, intonation expressiveness, speech etiquette, speech development, process of communication.

Introduction.

Speech as the highest mental function is the most important component of intellectual activity, and language as the leading means of realizing speech activity and implementing thought processes has been the subject of close attention of specialists studying psychology and linguistics for a long time.

Theoretical and experimental studies conducted within the framework of the above-mentioned sciences have allowed us to accumulate and summarize sufficient material characterizing the general laws of language acquisition and the formation of human speech abilities in the process of ontogenesis, features characterizing the processes of speech activity in society. Numerous studies have been devoted to the problem of the culture of speech communication by scientists who represent the psychological and linguistic school (P.P. Blonskiy, L.S. Vygotskiy, S.L. Rubinstein, A.R. Luria, A.N. Leontiev, L.V. Shcherba, V.V. Vinogradov, etc.).

The essence of the culture of speech communication is a personality quality that includes a culture of speech, a culture of thinking, an emotional culture and presupposes mastery of the norms of the literary language, the ability to adequately choose and use means of communication in solving the set communicative tasks. This quality implies knowledge and observance of speech etiquette by a younger student, the ability to use the means of intonation expressiveness of speech; the ability to enrich vocabulary and logical thinking.

Let's consider the conditions for successful speech development and formation speech skills in children, which form the basis of the culture of speech communication:

- the need for communication, or communication.

Research methods

The process of communication is possible only when the interlocutors use generally understandable signs, namely words, their combinations, and various turns of speech. This means that in the process of speech development, situations are provided that determine the motivation of speech, forcing the student to use speech utterances that arouse his interest and desire to talk about something.

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This means that children need to be provided with the most frequently used speech samples, or create a

speech environment that activates the child's process of assimilation of these speech samples.

- speech, in addition to the function of communication, also performs a cognitive function, helping the child not only to build the process of communication with others, but also to actively explore the world. Mastering speech is one of the ways to know reality. Such speech characteristics as diversity, accuracy, and content directly depend on the degree of enriching the child's consciousness with various ideas and concepts.

In other words, speech, in the process of its development, is necessary not only linguistic, but also in the actual material. It should be noted that this material should be socially or personally significant. This is also a necessary condition for the child's speech development. And vice versa: the more freely a person enjoys various opportunities to use all the richness of his native language, the stronger his numerous connections with society and with the surrounding reality become. For every child, fluency in speech skills is a prerequisite for successful socialization, and as a result, successful learning and development.

At school, the child is given the opportunity to learn literary language in its artistic, scientific and colloquial versions. This is a fairly extensive block of information, including more than one thousand new words and new meanings, a large number of such combinations and syntactic constructions that were not previously used in the speech activity of a preschooler. Parents are not always aware of how important this activity is, assuming that daily communication with an adult and regular reading of books are enough for the child. But such presentations can negatively affect the system of formation of speech activity of a younger student, because the system of enrichment and development of children's speech requires systematic work, which in a certain way doses the necessary material - vocabulary, syntactic constructions, types of speech, etc.

In the process of developing students' speech, the teacher sets clear goals for the formation of certain speech characteristics in students, which are criteria for evaluating students' oral and written statements:

1. Mastering the rules of the literary language, which obey the norms, the ability to distinguish literary and non-literary language, as well as literary language from vernacular, dialects, jargons.

In the process of this work, it is necessary to apply a system of educational influences on students, systematic work is required, which accordingly and definitely doses the educational material, strict observance of steps in the process of speech formation is necessary.

2. Mastering the processes of reading and writing by students. Reading and writing are speech skills and skills that They are based on a language system, based on its phonetic, lexical, graphic and spelling rules, as well as on the process of perceiving other people's speech. In the process of mastering written speech, students must master various features of genres: description, narration, writing, newspaper article, reasoning.

One of the main requirements is the requirement of meaningful speech. If the student's story is based on interesting facts, interesting observations and thoughtful thoughts, sincere experiences will be present in it, it will be very interesting and useful to others and to himself. In elementary school, the process of forming artistic speech must begin with a folk tale, in which a full range of artistic techniques can be found in large numbers, which will be extremely useful to a younger student. The teacher needs to use the processes taking place in the ordinary the student's life, namely excursions, watching animated and feature films, hiking, books read, special observations, all this is the main content of preparatory conversations, and the basis for subsequent written essays, stories, etc. At the same time, it must be remembered that the events used should have a positive emotional coloring for the child, be for They are interesting and instructive for him.

The second is the requirement of the ability to logically, consistently and clearly construct speech. Confident knowledge of the information that the student speaks or writes about helps him not to miss anything important, allows him to build logical transitions from one part to another, not to repeat himself in his statements.

Results.

The above requirements should apply to the speech of younger students. A child can receive a characteristic of correctly delivered speech only if it meets all the listed requirements. In elementary school, it is considered a big mistake to work only on certain aspects of speech, for example, spelling literacy, and other types of work would be transferred to high school. Unfortunately, this error is present in practice. It is not always possible to work at each lesson on the variety of speech tools used by students, on the requirement of clarity of speech, carefully choosing words from a number of synonyms, teach children to correct speech defects in their comrades and improve their own speech.

Speech is a diverse human activity that is used to communicate, to convey one's thoughts, one's knowledge, intentions, and feelings. Speech is multifaceted and in different situations we observe its various forms, for example: this is an artistic monologue, delivered from the stage and the speaker's speech, scientific work and a speech to the team, a conversation between classmates or a conversation with a teacher.

Accordingly, activities in the field of speech development cannot be monotonous. The teacher needs to know the specifics of each type of speech [E. Rodionova, 2006.p.85]. Speech is not presented without

communication. The most common form of communication is dialogue. A dialogue is a conversation between two or more people. The remarks of the interlocutors have a direct impact on one another and are interdependent. Dialogic cues are also influenced by the situation that develops during the dialogue. There is a large number of incomplete sentences in the dialogue, since in the presence of voluminous, detailed sentences, the meaning of the dialogue is lost, its liveliness and fluidity disappear. One of the characteristic features of the dialogue is the presence of interrogative and exclamation sentences, interjections, particles indicating the high emotionality of the interlocutors. The syntactic component of dialogues is usually simplified.

Conversation is an artificial form of dialogue, actively used in English language lessons at school. It differs from direct dialogue by using complete sentences. The conversation is aimed at teaching students the correct construction of sentences, introducing them to the use of literary speech in dialogue.

Thus, observing the conditions for the formation of speech culture in primary school children, the assimilation of the basic communicative function of speech contributes to the development of thinking, socialization of younger schoolchildren, develops interest in the world around them, helps the child to fully develop his abilities, which leads to the formation of a socially active personality.

Great attention should be paid to the presence of feelings of satisfaction among students from the results of their work, to control their emotional interest in the process of preparing and implementing the results of monologue speech. The teacher should constantly strive to create situations as a result of which students felt satisfaction and joy from their stories and writings. Speech for a student should not be just a learning exercise, after completing which he will receive an appropriate grade. It is necessary to ensure that the speech for the child, it became a means of self-expression and an object of joy and pride. In this process, the teacher will be helped by timely motivation for the development of speech activity, which should lead to the need for students to speak, write, and participate in performances.

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Dialogical speech is impossible without the interlocutor's remarks and questions corresponding to the situation. This makes it much easier to build a dialogue. The process of developing monologue speech is much more complicated, the types of which These include a story, an essay, a message, a report, a retelling, a speech at a meeting, etc. The listed types of oral and written monologue should be the focus of the primary school teacher's attention and be solved in a timely manner, using modern methods, in English language and literary reading lessons starting from the first grade of elementary school.

Monologue, coherent speech is often presented in writing. Written speech has the same properties as oral monologue, but they are much more clearly expressed.

In this case, there are higher requirements for such concepts as sentence construction, word choice, logic, completeness of the topic, consistency of presentation, correctness of language. At the same time, there are also distinctive features of writing.

Firstly, written speech is completer and more complex than oral speech. It includes more extended sentences, used designs that significantly complicate the offer. Observations have shown that in the written version, the size of the composition (story) exceeds the size of a similar oral story.

Secondly, the written version cannot reflect the existing pauses, logical accents, intonation, gestures and other means that are important and affect the meaning of oral speech. This is a significant disadvantage of writing. To some extent, this disadvantage is mitigated by the presence of punctuation marks, the fact that the text is divided into paragraphs, and the font can be highlighted in font or underline, and additional remarks can be made.

Thirdly, writing is complicated by spelling, and it is not easy for younger students. It is a well-known fact that some students write short texts of essays because they are afraid to make a lot of spelling mistakes. An unformed spelling skill is a rather serious problem in solving the problems of developing children's written speech, therefore, the teacher needs to have a method of spelling preparation of students for composition and presentation.

As a result, the process of writing is much slower than oral, especially in elementary grades, while often this processes It turns into an end in itself for primary school students and at the same time they forget about the content of the text and the choice of language tools.

Written speech is a prepared speech that can be checked and necessary adjustments can be made, which is why it is difficult to overestimate the importance of this process for improving the overall language culture of primary school students.

The main attention in the process of teaching children in primary school is paid to writing, as it is the basis for the subsequent study of almost all subjects of the school curriculum. Not forgetting the need for parallel development and the process of oral speech, the educational activity of a teacher, recently, It is aimed at developing this process in students. In primary school, children's speech activity takes a leading position in the development of new knowledge. Some students have character traits such as shyness, stiffness, which prevents them from answering teacher's questions, taking part in conversations and discussions.

The teacher, together with a psychologist, must work to identify such qualities in children and conduct appropriate work with such children. In the case when a teacher from the first grade teaches each student to participate in conversations without fear and embarrassment, to speak, to answer questions clearly, this will further greatly facilitate the child 's learning process in the subjects included in the educational program.

We also note that the reason for the low speech activity of children may be speech defects, in such cases, the teacher must be actively involved in the work parents and speech pathologists. In the first grade in elementary school, a significant proportion of attention is paid to the pronunciation side of speech, namely: the correct articulation of sounds, elements of speech therapy work, which are realized with the help of tongue twisters, recitations, chants, choral reading.

Primary school age is a period during which there is an intensive development of all sides of speech, therefore, the relationship of different speech tasks and the formation of coherence of statements during this period have a leading role. It is also important for a teacher to form and develop the ability to connect sentences with different types of communication and to build statements of different types – descriptive and narrative.

The purposeful development of all the above-mentioned aspects of speech, including the culture of speech communication, will prepare younger schoolchildren for the subsequent stages of improving coherent speech and in the sense of selection language tools, and the logic of creating a meaningful statement.

The decisive task of the process of developing speech culture is to teach students the ability to express their own and other people's thoughts in a meaningful, grammatically and stylistically correct way orally and in writing. A sufficient vocabulary allows the child to optimally accurately express his thought, therefore, work on expanding and The improvement of the dictionary is the basis of the process of improving oral speech.

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